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THE FABLE POETRY OF ABBASQULU AGHA BAKIKHANOV

Abstract.

Among the prominent representatives of nineteenth-century Azerbaijani literature, the literary work of A. Bakikhanov occupies a special place, particularly his writings for children. In these works, the poet sought to provide artistic expression to pedagogical and moral ideas, which was closely connected to his educational and enlightenment activities. These writings consist of moral advice, verse tales, and fables. Bakikhanov's fables such as *The Fox and the Sheep*, *Groundless Pride*, and *The Worm and the Snail*, which instill moral and ethical feelings in young readers, carry both simplicity and profound meaning. Drawn from real-life themes, these works, in the hands of the writer, acquire greater impact by encouraging children to value labor, effort, and kindness, while cultivating in children and youth a sense of aversion toward injustice, arrogance, groundless pride, and the negative quality of considering oneself superior to others. The present article examines the moral and social messages of these fables.

Keywords: A. Bakikhanov, children's literature, fable, idea-content, theme

Introduction

A. Bakikhanov was one of the prominent creators of nineteenth-century Azerbaijani children's literature. A significant part of his literary heritage consists of works dedicated to the education and upbringing of children and youth. His moral advice, verse tales, and fables that cultivate noble ideas were read and memorized with enthusiasm by schoolchildren. In his writings for children, Bakikhanov placed particular emphasis on moral and educational themes, which also found reflection in his fables. In his fables, Bakikhanov criticizes negative qualities in human character. This criticism acquires specific examples and meanings in his fables, calling on the reader to adopt an active stance in life (Hasanli, 2015).

Analysis

In the fable *The Fox and the Sheep*, he conveys to the reader the importance of caution, wise behavior, and the defense of the weak in human life. One day, a hungry fox, while roaming the steppe, comes across a lone sheep grazing. Although the fox wants to eat it, realizing it lacks the strength, it resorts to trickery.

He said: "O you with a hard body and an empty tail,

Such injustice cannot be pleasing to God.

This land comes from my forefathers,

What courage, what conscience do you have in this? (Bakikhanov, 2005).

The fox said to the sheep that these lands belonged to his forefathers. He demanded that the sheep pay him rent for grazing on this territory. The sheep did not believe the fox and replied that thousands of sheep like him grazed here. To prove his claim, the fox suggested bringing a witness, and the sheep agreed. The sheep told this story to his friend, the dog, while the fox recounted it to an old wolf he met on the road. The next morning, the dog came with the sheep to the place, dug a trench, hid inside it, and said to the sheep:

He said: "Go and graze, do not fear, be assured.

If the fox brings a witness, do not accept him.

Bring him to me for the oath,

Then you will see what I do with that witness"

(Bakikhanov, 2005)

The fox brought the wolf as a witness to the sheep. The sheep said that in order to believe them, they must swear an oath at the hearth. They agreed. When the fox approached the hearth, he saw two eyes shining there, drew back, and said to the wolf:

He said to the wolf:

"To swear an oath at the sacred place

Has never been the custom of our forefathers.

Now I am greatly afraid of this oath.

You swear it yourself, since you have no fear"

(Bakikhanov, 2005)

When the wolf approached the sacred place to swear the oath, the dog leapt out, seized him by the throat, and strangled him. Seeing this, the fox fled. The fable ends with the following moral lesson:

If you mercilessly oppress the powerless,

Some dog will take vengeance on you. (Bakikhanov, 2005)

In this fable, A. Bakikhanov illustrates both natural instincts and the importance of acting with wisdom and reflection. The language is simple, clear, and descriptive, which makes the text accessible to readers across different age groups. When portraying the characters, Bakikhanov presents their behavior and intentions in a direct manner. The fox is characterized by cunning and persuasive ability, whereas the sheep, although initially appearing weak, ensures his survival through intelligent action.

The central message of this fable is that those who seem weak may also be intelligent, and everyone must know how to defend themselves. At the same time, the work conveys to children and young people the importance of caution toward strangers and suspicious situations (Əsgərli, 2008).

The fable *Groundless Pride* critiques the human tendency to exaggerate personal abilities and achievements. Here, Bakikhanov highlights ego and arrogance.

The protagonist insists on displaying his skills and accomplishments to others, yet this ultimately results in self-harm.

In the fable, a gourd vine seed that has fallen beneath the plane tree, twines around it and, thanks to the tree, grows tall.

Embracing the plane tree, it quickly grew tall,
It raised its head higher than the plane.

It did not realize that thanks to the plane tree,

It had taken root and risen toward the sky.
(Bakikhanov, 2005)

Then it boasted, saying to the plane tree that in a short time it had grown taller than him, and soon the angels would pick its fruits.

If we keep embracing for several years,
Surely no one will ever reach me.

The lofty heavens will be a playground for me,

And angels will gather fruit from my branches.
(Bakikhanov, 2005)

Hearing this, the plane tree said to the gourd vine:

The plane tree laughed and said, "Do not boast yourself.

True strength will be revealed when the autumn wind begins to blow."

(A. Bakikhanov, 2005)

At that moment a strong wind blew, striking the gourd vine to the ground and destroying it.

The main idea of the fable is that a person should be modest about their abilities and achievements and avoid groundless pride. In this work, Bakikhanov also conveys norms of social behavior to the reader: in order to gain the respect of society, one must act correctly and sincerely rather than trying to present oneself as superior to others.

The simplicity of the language and the correspondence of the characters to the realities of life enhance the impact of the fable. Bakikhanov presents the gourd's ego and the superiority it seeks to display in such a way that the reader immediately perceives its baseless pride, realizing that excessive self-display and claims of greatness over others only lead to negative consequences. In the fable, the poet highlights the weak sides of human character through humor and irony, instilling moral qualities in the reader.

In *The Worm and the Snail*, Bakikhanov again emphasizes the bitter outcome of groundless pride. In this fable, he contrasts those who act quickly but thoughtlessly with those who behave patiently and wisely. In the plot, the worm and the snail are used to depict different character types. When an apple falls to the ground in the wind, the worm inside survives, and he considers this a heroic act, boasting to himself and saying:

Lifting up his form, he said: "I am the hero.

Neither wind nor storm can cause me harm."

(Bakikhanov, 2005)

At this moment, the worm proudly said to the snail, who was looking at him with mockery:

Looking with pride, he cried:

"Hey, look here,

See how brave I am."

Then rising a little higher,

He stood upright on the apple and said:

"I am a minaret.

Come closer, so that in my shadow

You may be protected from the wind."

(Bakikhanov, 2005)

The snail, however, did not listen to him and withdrew into its shell. Suddenly a strong wind blew, and the apple fell from the tree, destroying the worm. Watching this, the snail said:

Softly the snail said:

"Behold, this is the end of your fame,

Groundless boasting and pride has brought you to shame.

Believe this snail, a wisdom I lend:

To take refuge in one's own home

Is better than a foolish death in the end."

(Bakikhanov, 2005)

This fable shows the reader that in life patience and thoughtful behavior lead to success, while sudden and thoughtless actions result in failure. The worm is highly aggressive, and his groundless boasting leads nowhere because he makes rash decisions. The snail, on the other hand, moves slowly but acts with purpose and patience, and in the end reaches its goal. Through the figure of the worm, the fable demonstrates the negative consequences of impulsive choices and haste, while the figure of the snail emphasizes the value of patience and purposeful action.

The language of the work is simple, and the descriptions are clear, conveying meaning directly to the reader. This fable provides a moral lesson for both children and adults. At the same time, Bakikhanov conveys to the reader the realities of life: patience, reflection, and purposeful behavior are the keys to success.

The main feature of Bakikhanov's fables is their simple, clear, and effective language, through which they convey lessons to the reader. All three works – *The Fox and the Sheep*, *Groundless Pride*, and *The Worm and the Snail* – reflect different human behaviors and character traits (Namazov, 2007).

These fables teach the reader to be intelligent and humble, and to act with patience and reflection. Through animal figures, negative aspects of human character are criticized. The fox, the sheep, the worm, and the snail represent behaviors that are often encountered in human life.

Reflecting the realities of life, these fables instruct the reader on how to act wisely and correctly in situations that may be faced in daily life. Humor and irony are also present in Bakikhanov's fables. These elements enhance the reader's interest in the works and help the moral messages remain memorable.

Conclusion

A. Bakikhanov's fables hold an important place in Azerbaijani literature. Through the works *The Fox and the Sheep*, *Groundless Pride*, and *The Worm and the Snail*, he communicates human behaviors, character traits, and moral values to the reader. Each fable is distinguished by its simple and effective language, clear plot, and moral message. When drawing conclusions in his fables, Bakikhanov makes use of proverbs, sayings, and his own aphorisms, thereby deepening their mean-

ing (Qasımzadə, 2017). Reading these fables both entertains and makes the reader reflect, while at the same time imparting moral and social values that can be applied in life.

Thus, Bakikhanov's fables are of great moral and social significance in Azerbaijani literature. Their importance has not diminished in the modern era, since human character and behavior demonstrate similar features regardless of time.

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